

Assessing the Impact of Ulnar Styloid Fractures on Distal Radius Injury Recovery: A Prospective Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Distal radius fractures often co-occur with ulnar styloid fractures, leading to varied treatment approaches and debates on their impact on functional outcomes. This study aims to assess whether surgical repair of ulnar styloid fractures contributes to better functional outcomes in patients with distal radius fractures.

Material and Methods: Conducted at the Central Institute of Orthopaedics in New Delhi over 18 months, this prospective, comparative analysis included 60 patients with concurrent distal radius and ulnar styloid fractures. Patients were randomized into two groups: one undergoing distal radius fixation without ulnar styloid intervention and the other receiving fixation for both fractures. The study focused on evaluating postoperative complications, pain management (VAS scores) and functional recovery (DASH scores)

Results: No significant difference in age distribution was observed between the groups. Surgical duration was notably longer in the group receiving ulnar styloid fixation. However, this group demonstrated significantly better outcomes in pain reduction and functional recovery over time, without an increase in postoperative complications.

Conclusion: Surgical repair of ulnar styloid fractures, in conjunction with distal radius fractures, leads to improved pain management and functional outcomes without compromising safety. These findings suggest that addressing ulnar styloid fractures in the surgical protocol may enhance recovery and quality of life for patients with distal radius fractures.

Keywords: Distal radius fracture, ulnar styloid fracture, surgical treatment, Functional outcome, Pain management, DASH score.

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Introduction

Ulnar styloid fractures often accompany fractures of the distal radius, with reported occurrences ranging between 21% and 65%. Such fractures may lead to instability in the distal radioulnar joint and may co-occur with injuries to the triangular fibrocartilage complex. [1] In cases where ulnar styloid fractures are not treated, there is a 25–60% chance of non-union, even when the distal radius fracture has been stably fixed. [2]

The impact of ulnar styloid fractures on the functional outcomes of distal radius fractures is currently debated within the medical literature, with some research suggesting that these fractures can lead to worse outcomes for the distal radius fracture if left untreated, while other studies suggest no significant impact on wrist function or the stability of the distal radioulnar joint. [3] Research indicates that fractures occurring at the tip and waist of the ulnar styloid typically do not

have significant clinical consequences because the triangular fibrocartilage complex (TFCC) primarily attaches at the styloid's base. [4] Conversely, fractures at the base of the ulnar styloid are more likely to be associated with TFCC tears and instability in the distal radioulnar joint (DRUJ), which can result in chronic instability and reduced wrist function and mobility over time. [5] To mitigate such outcomes, the surgical repair of the ulnar styloid is often advocated. Despite this, the literature shows mixed results regarding the overall impact of ulnar styloid fractures on the outcomes of distal radius fractures, largely due to a lack of differentiation between the fracture sites on the styloid. [6]

Notably, fractures at the base of the ulnar styloid, which account for 41% of these injuries, are particularly concerning due to their implications for DRUJ stability and the potential for detachment of

the ulnar radial ligament. [7] Currently, there is limited research comparing the clinical outcomes, including range of motion and wrist function, between cases with and without surgical intervention for ulnar styloid fractures in the context of concurrent distal radius fractures. This study aims to fill that gap by evaluating whether surgical repair of the styloid base leads to better functional outcomes than nonsurgical management.

Material and Methods

The study was conducted at the Central Institute of Orthopaedics, Vardhman Mahavir Medical College, and Safdarjung Hospital in New Delhi over a period of one and a half years. It was designed as a prospective, comparative analysis focusing on patients with intra-articular fractures at the distal end of the radius and ulnar styloid. A total of 60 patients were included and divided into two groups of 30 each through a random number table method. One group underwent internal fixation of the distal radius without addressing the ulnar styloid fracture, while the other group received internal fixation for both the ulnar styloid and the distal radius fractures.

The study recruited skeletally mature individuals who had experienced an intra-articular distal radius fracture with a concurrent ulnar styloid fracture, provided they received intervention within a week of the injury.

Exclusion criteria included previous wrist injuries, pathological fractures, radio-carpal arthritis, polytrauma involving the ipsilateral extremity, metabolic disorders, pregnancy, and current corticosteroid therapy. Initial assessments followed the ATLS protocol, focusing on airway, breathing, circulation, and ruling out other major injuries. Emergency room management included

immobilization, IV fluids, and administration of analgesics, antibiotics, and tetanus toxoid. Further assessment involved detailed histories, clinical examination, x-rays, and classification of fractures using the Frykman system.

Preoperative preparation covered skin incision site assessments, routine investigations, consent verifications, equipment checks, and preoperative fasting and hydration. Surgical interventions utilized regional or general anesthesia, with prophylactic antibiotics administered beforehand. The surgical process involved precise incisions, exposure, and reduction techniques for the fractures, followed by fixation using precontoured plates. Postoperative care included antibiotics, immobilization, and gradual mobilization exercises, with ulnar styloid k-wire removal at six weeks.

Patients were monitored postoperatively at three, six, and nine months, focusing on surgical duration, complications, radiological alignments, pain management, range of motion, grip strength, pain evaluation, DASH scores, and radiological assessments of fracture healing and alignment.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were carried out using the SPSS 17.0 software package designed for social sciences. Continuous variables are reported as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD), while categorical variables are given as counts and percentages. The analysis of continuous variables that followed a normal distribution across the groups was conducted using the Student's t-test. For nominal categorical variables, comparisons between groups were made using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, depending on which was most suitable. A p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed to indicate statistical significance.

Table 1: Comparison of age distribution between group-1 and group-2

Age Groups	Group 1		Group 2		P Value
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	
19 - 20 yrs	2	6.7%	2	6.7%	0.994
21 - 30 yrs	13	43.3%	13	43.3%	
31 - 40 yrs	6	20.0%	6	20.0%	
41 - 50 yrs	5	16.7%	4	13.3%	
>50 yrs	4	13.3%	5	16.7%	
Total	30	100%	30	100%	
Mean \pm SD	34.80 \pm 11.75		35.60 \pm 13.44		0.807

The age distribution of the sixty patients (30 patients in each group) who underwent treatment for distal radius fractures either with or without ulnar styloid fracture fixation was similar.

The study includes individuals aged 19 to 50 years and older, with the 21-30 years group comprising the largest proportion (43.3 percent in both co-

orts). Group 1 had an average age of 34.80 years (SD = 11.75), while Group 2 had an average age of 35.60 years (SD = 13.44).

These p-values (0.994 for specific age groups and 0.807 for mean age comparison) do not indicate a statistically significant difference in the age distribution between the two groups.

Table 2: Comparison of Side Distribution between Group 1 and Group 2

Side	Group 1		Group 2		P Value
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	
L	17	56.7%	14	46.7%	0.438
R	13	43.3%	16	53.3%	
Total	30	100%	30	100%	

The analysis concentrated on the side distribution (L and R) in two groups, Group 1 and Group 2, each which includes 30 subjects. The percentage and frequency distributions of these sides were compared. In Group 1, thirteen participants (43.3%) were on the R side and seventeen individ-

uals (56.7%) were on the L side. In contrast, Group 2 consisted of sixteen subjects (53.3%) on the R side and fourteen subjects (46.7%) on the L side. The statistical analysis revealed that, with a p-value of 0.438, there was no significant difference in the side distribution between the two groups.

Table 3: Comparison of Duration of Group surgery, Intraoperative Complications and Immediate Postoperative Malalignment between Group 1 and 2

Outcome	Group 1 (n=30)	Group 2 (n=30)	P Value
Duration of Surgery in Hours (Mean \pm SD)	49.67 \pm 8.80	62.33 \pm 7.04	<0.001
Intraoperative Complications	No complications (100%)	No complications (100%)	-
Immediate Postoperative Malalignment	No malalignment (100%)	No malalignment (100%)	-

Significant differences were observed primarily in the duration of surgery when comparing Group 1 and Group 2 with regard to intraoperative complications, immediate postoperative malalignment, and duration of surgery. The average duration of surgery for Group 1 was considerably

shorter than that of Group 2 (62.33 \pm 7.04 hours vs. 49.67 \pm 8.80 hours), with a p-value below 0.001. There were no instances of instantaneous postoperative malalignment or intraoperative complications reported by either group, alignment outcomes were comparable.

Table 4: Comparison of VAS between Group 1 and Group 2

VAS	Group 1 (n=30)	Group 2 (n=30)	p- Value
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	
Post op	79.83 \pm 6.64	79.97 \pm 7.24	0.941
6 weeks	25.87 \pm 1.74	16.00 \pm 3.50	<0.001
3 months	16.00 \pm 3.50	2.77 \pm 0.86	<0.001
6 month	10.90 \pm 1.63	0.00 \pm 0.00	<0.001
9 month	2.07 \pm 1.39	0.00 \pm 0.00	<0.001

There was no statistically significant difference observed in the pain levels of Group 1 and Group 2 as measured by the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) immediately following the operation (79.83 \pm 6.64 vs. 79.97 \pm 7.24, p=0.941).

In contrast, Group 2 exhibited noteworthy progress as time progressed, as evidenced by VAS scores

declining considerably more than Group 1 did at the following time points: six weeks (16.00 \pm 3.50 vs. 25.87 \pm 1.74), three months (2.77 \pm 0.86 vs. 16.00 \pm 3.50), six months (0.00 \pm 0.00 vs. 10.90 \pm 1.63), and nine months (0.00 \pm 0.00 vs. 2.07 \pm 1.39).

All with p-values below 0.001.

Figure 1:

Table 5: Comparison of DASH score Points between Group 1 and Group 2

DASH	Group 1 (n=30)	Group 2 (n=30)	P Value
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	
6 weeks	67.77 ± 1.52	63.90 ± 1.56	<0.001
3 months	45.74 ± 1.67	19.96 ± 3.76	<0.001
6 month	19.96 ± 3.76	4.44 ± 0.91	<0.001
9 month	1.73 ± 0.90	0.00 ± 0.00	<0.001

Major differences were observed in the DASH scores, which are utilized to assess the physical function and symptoms of upper limb disorders, between Group 1 and Group 2 at every time point analysed.

Group 1 had a mean DASH score of 67.77 ± 1.52 at the 6-week mark, while Group 2 had a mean DASH score of 63.90 ± 1.56, this difference was statistically significant (p0.001). At three months,

Group 2 demonstrated significant advances over Group 1 (19.96 ± 3.76 vs. 4.44 ± 0.91), followed by Group 2 at nine months (1.73 ± 0.90 vs. 0.00 ± 0.00) with differences of 45.74 ± 1.67 and 19.96 ± 3.76 (p<0.001 at each time point).

This finding suggests that Group 2 exhibited a considerably more rapid and conspicuous amelioration in symptoms and functionality of the upper limbs throughout the duration of the study.

Figure 2:

Discussion:

Over two centuries have elapsed since the first description of a fracture at the distal radius by Colles. This type of fracture, despite being common, continues to pose significant challenges to both orthopedic and general surgeons. Young patients tend to suffer from comminuted distal end radius fractures due to high-energy impacts, whereas older individuals usually experience these fractures as a result of low-energy falls, leading to both shear and impacted fractures of the distal radius's articular surface along with fragment displacement.[8]

Distal radius fractures that exhibit dorsal displacement, comminution, and wrist joint involvement (intra-articular fractures) are considered more complex and severe. Historically, less stable fractures of this nature were managed using methods like percutaneous pinning or external fixation, or sometimes a combination of the two. However, there has been a significant shift towards open reduction and internal fixation with the advancement of internal plate fixation techniques. A poll among the American Society for Surgery of the Hand members revealed a preference for plate fixation in managing unstable distal radius fractures, with a minor preference for placing the plate on the volar side rather than the dorsal side. Recent biomechanical research comparing the stability of pin fixation to plate fixation, and evaluating volar locked plate fixation against both volar and dorsal unlocked plate fixation, found that volar locked plates offer superior stability and minimal fracture gap formation during testing on synthetic bone models. This present investigation focuses on employing volar locking internal fixation plates for all participants with distal radius fractures. The study conducted at the Central Institute of Orthopaedics, Vardhman Mahavir Medical College, and Safdarjung Hospital in New Delhi provided a comprehensive analysis of the functional outcomes of intra-articular fractures of the distal radius, with a specific focus on the impact of ulnar styloid fracture fixation. This prospective, comparative study, encompassing 60 patients divided into two groups, offers valuable insights into the benefits of addressing the ulnar styloid fracture in conjunction with the distal radius fracture. The meticulous methodology and statistical analysis employed emphasize the rigor of the investigation, contributing to its relevance in the field of orthopedics.

In our analysis shown in Table 1, we observed that the incidence of distal radius fractures with accompanying ulnar styloid fractures predominantly occurred between the third to fifth decades of life, with the average age being 34 years in the first group and 35 years in the second group, spanning ages 20 to 60 years. This contrasts with Buijze and colleagues, who found in their study of 36 individuals that these fractures typically occurred from the

fourth to the sixth decades, with an average age of 54 years, ranging from 25 to 75 years.[9] Similarly, Zenke and his team, in their research involving 118 participants, observed these fractures across the fourth to seventh decades, with a mean age of 64.1 years, and an age range of 25 to 94 years.[10] Kim and his team noted in their study of 138 patients that fractures were most frequent in the fourth to sixth decades, with an average age of 49 years, and ages ranging from 17 to 88 years.[11] Souer and his team, in a larger study with 376 patients, also reported fractures predominantly occurring in the fourth to sixth decades, with an average age of 55 years, and a range from 18 to 83 years. [12] The younger age group observed in our study for the high incidence of distal radius fractures with ulnar styloid fractures could be due to the high number of road traffic accidents in our region.

In our study Table 2 shows that 31 cases with left-sided fractures compared to 29 on the right, indicating a slight but not statistically significant inclination towards the left side. This finding is in line with Zenke and associates, who in their analysis of 118 patients, found 58 with right-side involvement and 60 with left-side, further highlighting the lack of significant dominance in fracture occurrence between sides.[10]

Surgical Duration and Safety: Table 3 shows the significant difference in the duration of surgery between the groups, highlighting the added complexity and time demands of ulnar styloid fracture fixation. Despite these differences, the absence of intraoperative complications and immediate postoperative malalignment in both groups is noteworthy, indicating that both surgical approaches are safe and effective in achieving initial fracture stabilization. This finding reassures clinicians about the feasibility of ulnar styloid fixation without compromising patient safety. In the study conducted by Zenke et al., postoperative complications were observed in 10.2% (12 patients) of the participants.[10] This included tendon injuries in three patients (two involving the extensor pollicis longus and one affecting the flexor pollicis longus), nerve palsy in two patients (one case of carpal tunnel syndrome and one case involving the superficial palmar branch of the median nerve), one case of flexor tendinitis in the thumb, one patient with an incomplete radial artery injury, and five instances of symptoms related to the plate. There were no reports of deep infections or complex regional pain syndrome among the patients.

Pain Management: As shown in Table 4, the VAS scores, revealed a crucial aspect of patient recovery. The absence of significant differences immediately post-operation suggests that both techniques are initially effective in managing pain. However, the significant improvements in VAS scores over time in Group 2 demonstrate the long-term benefits

of ulnar styloid fixation in enhancing pain relief. This suggests that addressing the ulnar styloid fracture may contribute to a more favorable pain management outcome, which is a critical component of patient satisfaction and recovery quality.

In a randomized clinical trial that compared the initial efficacy of distal radius fracture fixation and ulnar styloid fracture fixation in pain management, Group 2 demonstrated significant long-term relief from pain effects. [13] Pain and function were not significantly different between surgical and conservative treatments for ulnar styloid fractures, according to a second study. However, cases that underwent conservative treatment had a higher risk of non-union. [14] According to a study, there was no statistically significant relationship between the union status of ulnar styloid fractures and the severity of ulnar-sided pain.[15] An investigation comparing early and late fixation of ulnar styloid base fractures found that early surgical intervention within three months of injury resulted in more favourable outcomes, such as decreased pain scores and enhanced function. [16]

Functional Recovery:

The DASH scores as reported in Table 5, reflect the functional status and symptoms of upper limb disorders. They demonstrate a marked improvement in Group 2 across all follow-up intervals. This significant enhancement in physical function and symptom relief highlights the potential benefits of ulnar styloid fixation in facilitating a faster and more pronounced recovery process.

Such outcomes are essential for patients' return to daily activities and overall quality of life, making a case for the incorporation of ulnar styloid fixation in standard treatment protocols for intra-articular distal radius fractures with associated ulnar styloid fractures. In their research series, Zenke and colleagues reported significant improvements in the mean DASH scores across all groups, with no notable differences observed between them when analyzed using the Mann-Whitney U test. [10] The overall hand performance outcomes were classified as excellent in 73% (86 individuals), good in 22% (26 individuals), and fair in 5% (six individuals).

Clinical Implications:

The findings from this study have several implications for clinical practice. Firstly, they support the surgical intervention for ulnar styloid fractures in cases of intra-articular distal radius fractures, suggesting that improved patient outcomes justify the additional time and complexity.

Secondly, the study contributes to the ongoing discussion about optimal treatment strategies for distal radius fractures, advocating for a comprehensive approach that addresses all elements of the injury.

Future Research Directions:

While the study provides compelling evidence supporting ulnar styloid fixation, further research is needed to explore long-term outcomes, including the risk of osteoarthritis, the durability of pain relief, and functional recovery. Additionally, studies incorporating larger sample sizes and diverse populations could further validate these findings. Investigating patient-reported outcomes and quality of life measures would also offer a more holistic view of the impact of these surgical approaches on patients' lives.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study presents a strong argument in favor of ulnar styloid fixation when treating intra-articular fractures of the distal radius, based on the improved pain management and functional outcomes observed. These findings encourage a reevaluation of current treatment protocols and support a more inclusive approach to fracture management. As the field of orthopedics continues to evolve, such research is invaluable in guiding clinical decision-making and enhancing patient care.

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